

**LANGUAGE AND CULTURE IN ENGLISH CLASSROOMS: WAYS OF
ADDRESSING, EXPRESSING POLITENESS**

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Abstract: In this article, the duration of speaking in the English language, the effectiveness and benefits of communication, and the types of its use are covered. There are ideas about what words to use when having a dialogue with partners in English, and how to decorate the language room.

Key words: Communication, addressing, politeness, english classrooms, language.

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены продолжительность разговора на английском языке, эффективность и польза общения, а также виды его использования. Есть идеи, какие слова использовать при общении с партнерами на английском языке и как украсить языковой кабинет.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникация, адресация, вежливость, занятия английским языком, язык.

In an English classroom, it is important to address and express politeness in various ways. Some ways to do this include:

1. Using formal language: When speaking to the teacher or classmates, it is important to use formal language to show respect. This includes using titles such as "Mr.", "Ms.", or "Professor", and using polite phrases such as "please" and "thank you". It is important to use formal language in the classroom in order to maintain professionalism and create a respectful learning environment. This includes using proper grammar, avoiding slang or colloquial language, and addressing others with respect and courtesy. By using formal language, students are encouraged to communicate in a clear and articulate manner, which can promote better understanding and comprehension of the material being taught. Additionally, using formal language helps to set a tone of seriousness and importance in the classroom, which can enhance the overall learning experience for all students.

2. Being respectful: It is important to be respectful towards others in the classroom by listening to them when they are speaking, not interrupting, and acknowledging their ideas and opinions. This is essential for creating a positive and productive learning environment. Here are some tips on how to be respectful in the classroom: Listen to others without interrupting and wait your turn to speak. Treat your classmates, teachers, and other school staff with kindness and courtesy. Avoid disruptive behaviors such as talking out of turn, making loud noises, or using your phone during class. Participate actively in class discussions and activities, showing that you are engaged and interested in learning. Be mindful of your language and tone when communicating with others, using polite and respectful language. Respect the opinions and perspectives of your classmates, even if you may not agree with them. Follow classroom rules and guidelines set by your teacher, including arriving on time, completing assignments on time, and respecting the learning environment. By

practicing these tips, you can contribute to a positive and respectful classroom atmosphere that benefits everyone involved in the learning process.

. Using appropriate language: It is important to use appropriate language in the classroom, avoiding slang or offensive language. This demonstrates consideration for others and helps to create a positive and inclusive learning environment. It is important to use professional and respectful language in the classroom to create a positive and productive learning environment. This includes avoiding slang, profanity, or derogatory language. It is also important to use clear and concise language to ensure that students understand the material being presented. Additionally, using inclusive language that respects diversity and promotes a sense of belonging for all students is crucial in creating an inclusive and welcoming classroom environment.

4. Being mindful of body language: Body language can also convey politeness in the classroom. This includes making eye contact, nodding to show understanding, and having open and welcoming body language. Body language plays a crucial role in classroom communication and can greatly impact the learning environment. Here are some tips for being mindful of body language in the classroom:

Maintain good posture: Sitting or standing up straight can convey confidence and attentiveness. Slouching or hunching over may give the impression of disinterest or lack of engagement. Make eye contact:

Eye contact helps to establish a connection with students and shows that you are actively listening and engaged. Avoid staring or looking away too often. Use gestures effectively: Using appropriate hand gestures can help to emphasize key points or clarify information.

However, excessive or distracting gestures can be counterproductive.

Watch your facial expressions: Your facial expressions can convey a

wide range of emotions, so be mindful of how you are expressing yourself. A smile can create a positive and welcoming atmosphere, while a furrowed brow may signal confusion or frustration. Be mindful of personal space: Respect personal space boundaries and be aware of how your proximity to students may affect their comfort level. Allow for space and be conscious of not invading their personal space.

Mirror and match body language: Mirroring or matching the body language of students can help to build rapport and establish a connection. Pay attention to their nonverbal cues and adjust your body language accordingly. **Be aware of cultural differences:** Different cultures may have varying norms and interpretations of body language. Be sensitive to cultural differences and ensure that your gestures and expressions are respectful and appropriate. By being mindful of your own body language and paying attention to the nonverbal cues of your students, you can create a positive and inclusive learning environment in the classroom.

5. **Offering help and support:** Being polite in the classroom also means offering help and support to classmates when needed. This can include assisting with assignments, clarifying concepts, or being a supportive listener. By incorporating these strategies into the classroom environment, students can create a respectful and positive atmosphere that promotes learning and cooperation. As a teacher, it is important to create a safe and supportive classroom environment where students feel comfortable seeking help and support when needed. Here are some ways you can offer help and support to your students:

Be approachable and accessible: Let your students know that you are available to help them and encourage them to come to you with any questions or concerns they may have. **Provide individualized support:** Take the time to get to know each student and understand their

specific needs and learning styles. Offer personalized assistance to help them succeed. Encourage peer collaboration: Foster a sense of community in your classroom and encourage students to work together and support each other. Peer tutoring and group projects can help students learn from one another. Offer additional resources: Provide extra materials, resources, and tools for students who may need additional support. This could include worksheets, online resources, or access to tutoring services. Create a positive learning environment: Be encouraging and positive in your interactions with students. Celebrate their successes and offer constructive feedback to help them improve. By offering help and support in the classroom, you can create a supportive learning environment where all students feel valued and can thrive academically.

In conclusion, it is important for English classrooms to emphasize the value of politeness in communication. By teaching students various ways of addressing and expressing politeness, we can help them navigate social interactions effectively and respectfully. Through modeling and practice, students can develop the language skills and cultural awareness necessary to show consideration and courtesy in their interactions with others. Ultimately, fostering a culture of politeness in the classroom can lead to more harmonious relationships and successful communication in a diverse and interconnected world.

References:

Хужамуродова, Ф. П. Politeness and lexical means of expressing it in English / Ф. П. Хужамуродова.

Alan J. Fridlund (1994). Human facial expression (1 ed.). San Diego: Academic Press. ISBN 978-0-12-267630-7.

J.A. Russell; J.M. Fernandez Dols (1997). The psychology of

facial expression (1 ed.). Cambridge University Press. ISBN 978-0-521-58796-9.